

Efficacy of Concept Mapping Strategy on Academic Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Katsina, State Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of concept mapping strategy on academic performance in Biology among secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. The study was guided by two research objectives, corresponding research questions and null hypotheses, respectively. The study employed pre-test, post-test, quasi-experimental, control group research design. The population covered 6,942 male and female students in SS II from 22 public secondary schools in the study area. The sample of the study comprised 146 students. Biology performance Test (BPT), with reliability coefficient of 0.76 was used for data collection. Mean and Standard deviation was used to answer research questions while t-test independent were used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there is significant differences in academic performance score between students taught Biology concept using Concept Mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method. Based on the findings it was concluded that concept mapping strategy served as a better strategy in improving students' academic performance in Biology. The study recommends among others that Biology teachers should employ the concept mapping strategy in teaching Biology at senior secondary school level.

Keywords: Concept Mapping Strategy, Biology, Academic Performance

Introduction

Biology is one of the most important subjects in science that focuses on living things in the environment and also prerequisite for many fields that contribute immensely to the technological growth (Goji, 2018). The teaching of biology starts from senior secondary to tertiary institution and it served as prerequisite to the study of medicine, biochemistry, zoology and other science related courses (Atiku, 2020). Its therefore becomes binding on anyone wishing to offer or study any of the mentioned courses or any related course to offer Biology as a core subject apart from English, mathematics, physics and chemistry. Biology is concerned with the study of life and living organisms including their structure, function, growth, origin, evolution, taxonomy and distribution of living organisms. Biology education is important in nation building considering the role it plays in various aspect in the economy and public life such as health, agriculture, crime detection, disease and pest control, population control and research (Mohammad & Saleh, 2020). It is important in many ways for both individual and societal development as seen in biotechnology and genetic engineering. Biology also concerns with body systems, such as digestive systems, circulatory systems, respiratory systems, nervous systems, excretory systems and transport systems.

Digestive systems is among the most important organs of the body that help in sustaining live of animals. Digestive system comprises organs and glands in the body that are responsible for digestion. Studies show that students perceive digestive system difficult to learn (West African Examination Council WAEC, 2020). This difficulty in learning this concept often reflected in poor academic performance in tests and examinations. This may be as a result of poor teaching strategies adopted by teachers in teaching the concept. Therefore, many researchers and science educators advocate the use of more innovative, result-oriented, and student-centred strategies like concept mapping strategy and other student-centered method that involve the total involvement of learners in the teaching and learning process. Opara (2011) noted that these students-centered teaching methods when use in teaching can ultimately and positively affect students understanding and improve their academic performance.

Academic performance refers to the degree of intellectual stimulation that student could receive from learning situation (Ya'u 017). Academic performance is the measurement of students' achievement across various academic subject which is officially measure using classroom performance, graduation rates and result from standardized test (Onasanya and Omosewo, 2011). Aminu (2017), assert that academic performance refers to expression, used to present pupil's scholastic standing within a short term. Lekan (2016), viewed academic performance as the term that indicates a student's achievement after completing a course or subject from an institution. It measures students' learning across various academic subjects, which is assessed by

formative and summative assessments in the same vein he defined it as the outcome of students' efforts to attain some educational goals.

Gender is a socio-culturally ascribed attribute which differentiates feminine from masculine and is used to describe certain characteristics of men and women which are naturally, culturally and socially determined while those that are biologically determined are regarded as sex (Oleabhielle, 2018). Gender is one of the factors interacting with performance in Biology and other sciences (Adeniran, Ochu and Atoo, 2018). However, studies on how it actually influences performance have till now reported conflicting results, implying contradicting evidences in academic performance of students due to gender. Some researchers like Jahun and Mmoh, (2016); Mari, (2017); Ifeakor, (2018), reported that female students have a higher performance and interest in Biology than male students. Some of the factors identified to have accounted for the observed differences in the performance of male and female students in Biology are sex role stereotyping, masculine image of science and feminine socialization process. Contrary to the above finding, Ekwueme and Umoinyang (2015), reported that gender influenced performance in the favour of male. According to Aiyedum, (2020); Danmole and Adeoye, (2021); found no significant difference in the performance of students due to gender. Instead, they opined that performance of both males and females can be affected by teaching and learning styles. There is need for teaching strategies that will enhance performance in digestive system concepts in Biology for both male and female Students. Hence, this study investigated the efficacy of concept mapping strategy in enhancing male and female students' academic performance.

The dwindling students' performance in science especially Biology has been a source of concern to all stakeholders. Various scholars (Emmanuel, 2016; Mamman, 2016; Yavuz, 2016; Agboola, 2017 & Herbert, 2020), revealed that teaching methods, inadequate qualified biology teachers, lack of instructional materials and non-availability of laboratory facilities (Goji, 2018). However, the researcher had also observed that the major contributing factor that leads to persistent poor academic performance by students in Biology is attributed to inappropriate use of a suitable teaching strategies. This has necessitated the Science Education Community to therefore, develop new tools for making students go beyond rote learning. Concept mapping however, is an effective teaching strategy that has been extensively used in teaching many subjects (Seham, *et al* 2018). It allows learners to externalize their thinking in a visual and verbal form to improve their understanding of learning. It also allows learners to extract important information relate ideas and represent them in a structured manner. In view of this, there is therefore the need to determine its effect on students' interest and performance in Biology among Senior Secondary Schools. Hence, the problem of investigation in this study, posed as a question is what is the effect of concept-mapping strategy on performance in Biology? In other words, this study is designed to determine the extent to which the exploration of concept mapping strategy to improve students' academic performance in Biology at senior secondary school level when compared to subjecting them to the conventional method of teaching the subject in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. The (2020 WAEC) result in Katsina state, confirm that only 33.9% of students passed according to the Report by Chief Examiner (2020 WAEC). Failure is a great problem, as it affects the students' performances in science in Senior Secondary Schools. This situation has created the need for more effective teaching alternative methods to addressing the situation.

Objectives of the study

1. Determine the difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
2. Examine the difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean academic performance scores of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those taught using lecture method in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?
2. What is the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy?

Research Hypotheses

1. **H₀₁:** There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
2. **H₀₂:** There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy.

Methodology

The study employed Pretest, Post-test, Post-post-test and Control group, Quasi-experimental design. The study used two groups; Experimental group and Control group (CG). The illustration of research design was mentioned below:

Research Design Illustration

Group 1: EG O₁ X₁ O₂ O₃

Group 2: CG O₁ X₀ O₂ O₃

Keys:

EG Experimental Group X₁ Treatment (Concept mapping strategy)

CG Control Group X₀ No treatment (Lecture method)

O₁: Pre-test

O₂: Post-test

O₃: Post-Posttest

Population of the Study

The population covered six thousand, nine hundred and fourty two (6,942), Male, and Female SS II Biology Students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina State-Nigeria.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size of the study consists of one hundred and fourty two (142) male and female SS II biology students using random sampling techniques.

Results

Research Question 1:

Determine the difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Table 1: Differences in the Mean performance score of Experimental Group I and Control group

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean difference
Experimental Group I	77	34.83	3.21	13.57
Control Group	69	21.26	3.03	

Table 1. Showed that the mean interest of students score in experimental group is (34.83) and that of control group is (21.26). The table indicate that, there is significant difference between the Experimental Group and Control Group with mean rank difference of (13.57). This indicated that, students taught biology using concept mapping strategy have high academic performance in biology than those exposed to lecture method.

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Research Question 2:

Examine the difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Table 2: Differences in the Mean performance scores between male and female students in experimental group

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean difference
Male	44	34.43	3.17	0.93
Female	33	35.36	3.23	

Table 2. Showed that the mean academic performance of female students in experimental group is (35.36) and that of male is (34.43), this indicated that, there exist significant difference between male and female students in experimental group with

mean rank difference of (0.93). This indicated that, female students taught biology using concept mapping strategy have high academic performance in biology than male students.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated were tested using t-test independent between the variables involved. The null hypotheses are rejected when the p-value is less than the alpha-value of 0.05 level of significance and otherwise is retained. The results are presented in tables below and followed by the interpretations as shown below:

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Table 3: t-test Analysis of students' Academic Performance between Experimental group and Control group.

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	P value	Remark
Experimental group I	77	34.83	5.46	114	26.18	0.010	*Significant
Control group	69	21.26	3.04				

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 3. The table showed that there exists a statistically significant difference in the mean ranks between the Experimental and Control Groups with t-value of 26.18 and p-value of 0.00. Since the p-value (0.00) is less than the alpha value (0.05), therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicated that there is significant difference between students' academic performance of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state.

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of performance scores between male and female students in Experimental group

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Df	t value	P value	Remark
Male	44	34.43	3.17	75	-1.27	0.7	*Significant
Female	33	35.36	3.23				

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 4. The table showed that there exists a statistically significant difference in the mean rank scores between the male and female in experimental group with t-value of -1.27 and p-value of 0.706. Since the p-value (0.706) is not less than the alpha value (0.05), therefore the null hypothesis is retained. This indicated that there is no significant difference between male and female students' academic performance taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state.

Summary of Findings

The findings revealed that:

1. There is significant difference in mean academic performance score of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

2. There is no significant difference in mean academic performance score of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in experimental group in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study showed that, there is significant difference in the academic performance of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method. It also revealed that there no significant difference in mean academic performance score of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in experimental group. The finding of this study agreed with the findings of Rabe (2022), investigated the effect of concept mapping strategy on students' performance in biology among senior secondary schools in Kankia Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state. The finding revealed that students exposed to concept mapping strategy, achieved more in biology than those exposed to lecture method. Sakiyo and Waziri (2015) investigated the use of concept mapping teaching strategy on biology secondary school students' academic achievement in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The test for quality of means was indicating significant difference, in mean academic performance scores between experimental and control groups, the experimental group have high achievement in biology than the control group.

Conclusion

Basically, there was a significant difference in mean academic performance scores of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method. There is no significant difference in mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy. Based on the findings it was concluded that concept mapping strategy served as better strategy in improving academic performance of students in Biology.

Recommendations

1. Biology teachers should employ the concept mapping strategy in teaching digestive system in secondary schools level.
2. Workshops, conferences and seminars should be organized to Biology teachers by Ministry of Education on the use of concept mapping strategy in teaching digestive system in senior secondary schools' level.

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